

A Study on Promotional Strategies Adopted By Street Vendors That Influence the Consumer's Buying Behaviour in Tirunelveli

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Abstract:

The informal sector has grown rapidly in developing countries and has also developed therefore, it has attracted increasing attention and more and more literature focusing on its different aspects. However, the study of promotion strategies adopted by Street Vending Companies have received little attention in the literature on the informal sector. The purpose of the study is to identify promotion strategies adopted by street vendors to promote their products and highlight in particular the most effective technique in promoting their influential street assets decision to skip consumers. The study uses the primary data collected through a thorough quantitative analysis for represent the street markets in Tirunelveli. The sample included 129 active street passers. Relevant data collected using a pretested questionnaire, they are then analysed using descriptive statistical techniques. The analysis has had several important consequences; since the study covers only a limited area, the results it cannot be generalized. Research proposals and recommendations for further research are presented.

Keywords: informal sector, promotion strategies, street vendors.

INTRODUCTION

The streets are spaces that allow us to interact with the city, to travel, work, play and meet. The roads can be perceived as the lineages of the city; the necessary avenues that transport all urban life from one place to another and everywhere in between. Similarly, the road is a space of invisibility. It is a place where the homeless can be absorbed, "informal" transactions can be embraced and the faceless individual can wander like an urban nomad. Yet there is a coherent series of actors that, although sometimes invisible, dominate the urban landscape of our cities. They are individuals who discover the road in its simplest form and

who better understand the daily difficulties of city users. They are a priceless economic heartbeat on the streets of Tirunelveli; the "street vendors".

Walking through the streets of Tirunelveli, one cannot help but notice the huge amount of commercial transactions that the hawkers in Tirunelveli carry out every day. From Fruits, Vegetables, Snacks, Dolls, Furniture, Flowers, Groceries items, Clothes, Fresh Juice and Shoes you can almost find everything for sale in the streets of Tirunelveli. Of course, we may have seen this kind of "street activity" in other Indian cities, but nothing can be compared to the volume of business that the streets of Tirunelveli run every day. These sellers are "smart" and know how to make a living.

The purpose of the study is to identify the various promotional strategies adopted by street vendors to promote their products and to highlight in particular the most effective technique for promoting their street goods that influence the decision-making process of consumers regarding purchase. From this point of view, street market consumers represent an interesting segment to study as a potential target segment generally overlooked by companies. This will help retailers understand the decision-making and selection process used by street market consumers and how income levels, employment and gender influence their consumption behaviour.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

As an informal and formal market and economy (Sherry, 1990), marketing experts have suggested that flea markets are generally aimed at lower-class or low-income consumers, but not exclusively (Belk et al., 1988). Sherman et al., 1985, Sherry, 1999). 1990; Yavas and Riecken, 1981). They offer not only a discounted retail space, new or second-hand, but also a shopping experience and cultural immersion for their consumers, as well as an opportunity to develop the ritual dimension of consumption (Belk et al., 1988, Maisel 1974, Rook 1985, Sherry 1990).

(David Mchardy Reid, Eugene H. Fram and Chi Guotai, 2010) studied the operations of 80 street vendors in Dalian, China. It shows that their activities (buying, selling and merchandising, for example) are very similar to those of permanently anchored small retailers and should therefore be able to provide similar social contributions.

According to Dholakia (1999), the reason for shopping is to make physical visits to a shopping site. It is considered a domestic task as well as a form of recreation, relaxation and entertainment. Shopping is also considered the most positive attribute of recreational and working activity (Dholakia, 1999).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study is to identify the different promotional strategies adopted by street vendors to promote their products and highlight, in particular, the most effective technique for promoting their street goods that influence marketing decisions. customer purchase.

METHODOLOGY ADOPTED

Development of the tool: To satisfy and achieve the objectives of the study, a qualitative methodology and quantitative techniques were used. The study was conducted in various street markets located in Tirunelveli, in the state of Tamil Nadu. The sample included 129 active street passers. Regarding the sample, 129 active road buyers were selected and sent to them with a structured questionnaire. The content and validity of the various declarations of the questionnaire have been verified with the help of experts in the field of marketing.

Data sources: primary and secondary data were collected for the study. Primary data was collected by conducting an example customer survey. Using a well-prepared and structured questionnaire, the primary data was collected by the interviewees. Secondary data was collected in magazines, magazines, reports and other books, as well as on websites of street vendors and the informal sector.

Data analysis: the main data collected were sorted, classified and tabulated in a format and analysed using statistical software for social sciences (SPSS 19.0). For the inference an appropriate statistical procedure was used as the descriptive analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- Promotional tools adopted by street vendors in Tirunelveli

Attractive display

The products were presented in an attractive way to attract the attention of consumers. Recent stocks and new store supplies are well-hung at the entrance to create an attractive effect on consumers. Couples are appropriately matched according to the combination of colors and layers with the clothing sets to be known. Jeans with tops, overlapping a jacket with inner shirts, tops paired with a stole or scarf around the neck, etc.

Brochures:

The brochures were used to educate people about the different categories and promotional programs available in stores. This strategy is typically used when stores are located within a market that does not have visual access to consumers. To attract consumers to

their stores, these vendors hire local kids to distribute brochures to consumers on the main market streets and guide them to the store.

Shout

This is the most popular way to attract consumers on their used goods from these street vendors. The call out offers quotes and offers on the products, in this way they attract the attention of consumers who move to the market. This strategy is advantageous for every customer who visits at least once and turns to the store, while interested consumers stop to check the offers.

Interesting offers:

Offers like low prices to know. all at a fixed cost, for example Rs.150, 200. These low-priced offers are called quickly and forcefully or affix a label to the goods that mention the prices. They also assure consumers of their quality and cost by saying "You will not receive this piece at this price on the market".

Word of mouth:

It has been shown that WOM is more powerful than printed information (Borgida and Nisbett, 1977), mainly because WOM information is considered more credible. Another reason for the power of WOM marketing is that WOM is always relevant and timely, is driven by customer needs and grows exponentially. For example, a person tells a story to five people, each with five others, who tell five more after that. WOM also uses human nature, feeding on the fact that many people consider themselves experts (Jerram, 2003). Because street vendors lack financial resources, this promotional tool is the most preferred and powerful way to reach consumers.

Personal selling:

The supplier has a face-to-face interaction with the potential customer in which he identifies the customer's interest and offers the product according to his needs. This is the best way to promote sales, as suppliers create good customer relationships by personally engaging in the sales process, accelerating repeat sales and spreading positive word of mouth.

Demographic profile of respondent

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.Gender		
a) Male	55	42.6
b) Female	74	57.4
Total	129	100.0
2.Age		
a) 16-24	64	50

b) 25-33	39	30
c)34-42	20	15
d) 43-51	5	4
e)52 and above	1	1
Total	129	100.0
3.Occupation		
a) Salaried	72	55.8
b) Self-Employed	10	7.8
c)Professional	5	3.9
d) Housemaker	2	1.6
e)Student	40	31.0
Total	129	100.0
4.Average Monthly Family Income		
a) Less than Rs. 10000 p.m.	35	27.1
b) Rs. 10001- Rs. 20000 p.m.	49	38
c)Rs. 20001- Rs. 30000 p.m.	18	14
d) Rs. 30001- Rs. 40000 p.m.	13	10
e)Rs. 40001 and above	14	11
Total	129	100.0

The table above shows that 57% of respondents were women and 42% were men. This means that women are more involved in street shopping. Maximum number buyers who buy in street markets belong to the age group between 16 and 33 years, which represents about 80% of the total number of respondents. The demographic data also reveal that employees are mainly involved in street shopping, which represents 56% and 31% of total respondents respectively. This can also be said because Mumbai has many workers and students who travel every day. This also results from the analysis that consumers who buy products in street markets belong to a medium-income group of about 60% of the respondents.

Descriptive Analysis

The following descriptive statistics were calculated using SPSS(19.0).

Sl. No.	Particulars	Mean Value		Total	F Test	P Value
		Male	Female			
1.	Attractive Display of merchandise influence my shopping decision.	2.76	3.96	3.36	4.130	.003**
2.	Positive Word of Mouth by my friends/family influence my shopping decision	3.17	3.58	3.38	3.562	.712
3.	The way of selling of the street vendors by calling out the prices of the product or offer on the product influence my shopping decision	2.30	3.17	2.74	2.461	.034*
4.	Street vendors distributing pamphlets with appealing offers influence my shopping decision	2.24	2.59	2.42	2.321	.054

5.	Attractive offers on the products influence my shopping decision.	3.38	3.44	3.41	3.134	.103
6.	Good customer relationship	3.53	3.37	3.45	1.468	.201

The effectiveness of promotional strategies to influence consumer's buying behaviours is being studied. Six commonly used strategies are declared using 6 instruction variables. The table above shows the overall average values of the variables studied.

The results show that positive word of mouth is the most effective strategy, with an average score of 3.38, followed by the good customer relationship with an average score of 3.45, the attractive offers on products with an average score of 3.41, the attractive display of products with an average score of 3.36, the call with an average score of 2.74 and the least effective strategy found is the distribution of booklets.

H₀1: There is no significant difference between gender and the promotional strategies adopted by street vendors.

From the above hypothesis it is clear that the strategy of attractive display of merchandise and the way of selling by calling out the prices of the product or offer on the product influence is rejected. The strategies positive word of mouth by friends/family, street vendors distributing pamphlets with appealing offers, attractive offers on the products and good customer relationship has been accepted.

For most street vendors, marketing is a basic process and consists mainly of calling people passing in front of the stand. Few employee suppliers have received training and therefore rely on their instinct to know when to call a potential customer. The only other form of marketing used is to offer a discount to a regular or important customer and spread positive word of mouth.

The study shows that few strategies used by street vendors to promote their products are related to the promotional strategies used in conventional marketing literature. Word-of-mouth strategy, which is the most effective promotional tool for street vendors, has a significant impact on consumer's buying behaviours and marketers have understood the utility of this marketing tool.

SUGGESTION

Less or investment promotion measures

1. Street vendors should emphasize the spread of positive word of mouth to consumers by presenting the product appropriately, in order to convey the right marketing message.

2. It is necessary to look for other ways to present products in an attractive way, for example by knowing the right combination of colour's, embellishing the right set of garments, stacking the products appropriately, concentrating the fashionable product by positioning it prominently, etc.

3. Personal selling is also an effective promotion measure by communicating appropriately with consumers. Due to the lack of education, the seller involved in the sales process does not approach the customer in a pleasant way. To overcome this problem, sales staff should be trained in communication skills, appropriate behaviours and certain behaviours. In this way, even the upper middle class and sophisticated people will be potential consumers.

Innovative promotion measures with minimal investments

1. Advertising column of interesting articles in the local newspaper / newspaper store.
2. Broadcast offers or fashion titles on Radio.
3. Communication in the media about local cables.

CONCLUSION

Most large and medium-sized companies know their strengths and weaknesses in the market. Moreover, they can study their competitors and know how to minimize and develop their basic skills. Small businesses and micro-enterprises like street vendors can also use key skills as a weapon to develop business strategies. Limited resources hinder strategic alternatives to street vendors. Due to the competitive resources of large and medium-sized companies, street vendors must carefully evaluate potential corporate strategies to identify distinctive competencies. Critically, street food vendors must decide on the market structure they compete for and the strategies they will follow. Many suppliers do not plan their business strategies to manage their activities; they combine strategies and achieve relatively little because they cannot afford to maintain them because of the high capital requirements. But, as suggested, street vendors should focus on minimal investment strategies such as positive word-of-mouth dissemination, an attractive exhibition and personal sales. Moreover, if their profit margins allow it, they can invest in suggested strategies such as radio, cable advertising or newspaper advertising. The analysis of this research document and the results obtained will provide marketing authorities with a solid basis on various factors to consider, in order to minimize the impact of organized retailers and focus attention on effective management strategies. street vending. The results above show the most important points that can be used to promote flea markets as retail platforms for balance of payments segments.

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